

PROBLEMS MET ON MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING TOWARDS OBSERVANCE OF THE EIGHT ROLES OF TEACHERS: AN ACTION PLAN

John Niño S. Aleman
Ramil S. Bulilan, EdD

*Bohol Island State University
Clarin Campus
Poblacion Norte, Clarin, Bohol, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15491648>

ABSTRACT

The main thrust of this study was to determine the relationship between the problems encountered in modular distance learning and the observance of the eight roles of teachers in the public elementary schools of Sagbayan District, Sagbayan, Bohol for the School Year 2022–2023. This study was conducted in response to the sudden changes in the educational system, which redefined the role of teachers from facilitators of learning to information providers. It aimed to determine whether the challenges brought about by modular learning delivery had any impact on how teachers performed their professional roles. The respondents of the study were all public elementary school teachers in the Sagbayan District. The researcher utilized a descriptive survey method with a researcher-made questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. The questionnaire was composed of three parts: the profile of respondents in terms of age, sex, and length of service; the problems met in modular distance learning; and the observance of the eight roles of teachers. Data were analyzed using simple percentage, weighted mean, Chi-square, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. Based on the findings, the study revealed that there was no significant relationship between the problems encountered in modular distance learning and the observance of the eight roles of teachers. This indicates that despite the challenges, teachers continued to fulfill their roles effectively and adaptively. The study concludes that teachers' professional responsibilities remain consistent regardless of the problems faced in modular learning

implementation. However, it is recommended that the Department of Education and school administrators provide training programs on the eight roles of teachers during times of crisis, as such topics are often not addressed in pre-service education.

Keywords: *modular distance learning, eight roles of teachers, teacher adaptability, public elementary schools, education during crisis*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers have been bombarded with problems in the implementation of modular learning that affected their roles as classroom managers. One is the role of being a facilitator of knowledge. If not properly addressed, it will mitigate the performance of the learners. Teachers' functions, however, are becoming less visible in the current environment, where there is less physical interaction between teachers and students. Teachers' roles have shifted from knowledge facilitators to information providers.

Dargo and Dimas (2021) of the University of Cordillera Philippines said that learners' General Weighted Average fell by 2.25 percent after Modular Distance Learning was implemented, indicating a significant difference in their academic performance. This is due to the insufficient interaction between the teacher and the students. In Sagbayan District, the writer found out that most teachers are now primarily focused on printing, checking, and recording assessment results. The teachers contend that their role in the implementation of modular learning is limited to giving students the fundamental teaching materials. Most elementary teachers were unable to conduct home visits and intervene with students because of the modules' preparation, reports, and series of webinars. It can be stressed that if there are fewer problems with the implementation of modular learning, it is expected that the better the roles of teachers will be. On the other hand, it is expected that teachers' roles will be less evident if there are many implementation issues with modular learning.

The role of teachers in any situation, whether pandemic or not must be observed always to cater to learners' needs. The more the role of teachers to be internalized, the better they will be in the implementation of modular learning. If this modular learning strategy is continued without intervention, the learners' achievement and performance will deteriorate. The District of Sagbayan teachers were mostly affected by this phenomenon. Thus, this investigation is deemed indispensable and in order.

The respondents in this study were elementary school teachers in the District of Sagbayan. In this district, modular print modality is applied. It has a significant impact on teachers' roles. Various studies had been conducted regarding modular distance learning, but most of them did not deal with how this affected the teachers' role in the classroom during the educative process. This makes the present study different from them.

The above-mentioned issues motivated the writer to conduct this study to assess the problems met on modular learning and the observance of the eight roles of teachers. Moreover, this study would like to determine the relationship of the problems met in the implementation of modular learning in regard to the profile of the respondents. The results of this study will serve as the foundation for developing intervention programs to address issues on modular learning and enhance teachers' roles to ensure high-quality learning even in unusual settings.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the relationship of the problems met by classroom elementary school teachers on modular distance learning towards their roles in a classroom in Sagbayan District during the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, this study sought for answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender and;
 - 1.3 length of service?
2. What are the problems met by the teachers in the implementation of modular distance learning approach?
3. What is the extent of the observance of the teachers in regard to the eight roles of teachers?
4. Is there a significant difference in the observance of the eight roles of teachers and their problems met on modular distance learning approach when grouped into their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the problems met by the teachers in the implementation of modular distance learning approach and their observance of the eight roles?
6. What action plan may be proposed to address the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive-correlational method using a set of questionnaires as the main tool in gathering the data to achieve the objectives of the study.

Calderon (2006) defined descriptive research as an intentional process of gathering, analyzing, classifying and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, trends and cause-effect relationships and then providing sufficient and accurate interpretation of data with minimal assistance from statistical methods. This design is used in the study to determine the relationship between the problems met on modular distance learning towards the observance of the eight roles of teachers. Furthermore, the researcher used the total population method to determine the number of respondents in

the study. The adopted and modified survey questionnaire was also used as a tool in gathering the data.

Research Environment

The locale of this study was the Sagbayan District, Sagbayan, Bohol. It is located southwest of Clarin and Northeast of Carmen. It is 13 kilometers away from Bohol Island State University Clarin Campus. Sagbayan District is composed of twenty-one (21) elementary schools with one hundred seventy-nine (179) elementary teachers.

The name of schools where the study was conducted are the following: Sagbayan Central Elementary School, Cabasakan Elementary School, Calangahan Elementary School, Canmano Elementary School, Canmaya Centro Elementary School, Canmaya Diot Elementary School, Kagawasan Elementary School, Katipunan Elementary School, Langtad Elementary School, Mantalongon Elementary School, Sagbayan Sur Elementary School, San Agustin Elementary School, San Antonio Elementary School, San Isidro Elementary School, San Ramon Elementary School, San Roque Elementary School, San Vicente Norte Elementary School, San Vicente Sur Elementary School, Sta. Catalina Elementary School, Sta. Cruz Elementary School, and Ubojan Integrated School.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were all the teachers in the above-mentioned schools in the elementary since the researcher utilized total population method in determining the number of respondents. Out of one-hundred seventy-nine (179) elementary teachers, only one hundred forty-eight (148) questionnaires were retrieved with a retrieval rate of 82.68%. It is composed of seven (7) teachers of Calangahan ES, eight (8) teachers of Canmano ES, six (6) teachers of Canmaya Centro ES, eight (8) teachers of Canmaya Diot ES, seven (7) teachers of Kabasacan ES, six (6) teachers of Kagawasan ES, seven (7) teachers of Katipunan ES, seven (7) teachers of Langtad ES, seven (7) teachers of Mantalongon ES, nineteen (19) teachers of Sagbayan Central ES, eight (8) teachers of Sagbayan Sur ES, six (6) teachers of San Agustin ES, five (5) teachers of San Antonio ES, six (6) teachers of San Isidro ES, six (6) teachers of San Ramon ES, five (5) teachers of San Roque ES, six (6) teachers of San Vicente Norte ES, three (3) teachers of San Vicente Sur ES, seven (7) teachers of Sta. Catalina ES, five (5) teachers of Sta. Cruz ES, and nine (9) teachers of Ubojan Integrated School.

Research Instrument

The instrument has 3 parts. Part 1 is about asking for information regarding the profile of the respondents in regard to age, sex distribution and length of service. Part 2 is the adopted tool from the study of Alvarez (2021) on the issues and concerns of teachers In Mindanao State University-Sulu towards modular distance learning approach consisting of fifteen (15) items and Guiamalon et al. (2021) on the issues and concerns in the implementation of modular learning modality consisting of five (5) items. And part 3 is adopted by Koca et al. (2021) on the questionnaire to assess a teacher's perception

of their current personal commitment and preferred future commitment to each of the eight roles. The said tool was developed by Harden and Lilley (2018). It is consisted of two (2) items for the role information provider and coach, five (5) items for the role facilitator and mentor, five (5) items for the role assessor and diagnostician, four (4) items for the role curriculum developer and implementer, three (3) items for the role as role model as a teacher practitioner, three (3) items for the role manger and leader, four (4) items for the role scholar and researcher and three (3) items for the role professional. These tools have been validated to have reached the reliability index (Alvarez 2021; Guiamalon et al. 2021; Koca et al. 2021).

Research Procedure

During the data gathering, the writer wrote a formal written request to the Campus Director of Bohol Island State University Clarin Campus regarding the approval on the conduct of the study. Having granted approval, the writer wrote letter of permission to the Schools Division Superintendent of Bohol and District Supervisor of Sagbayan, Bohol for approval. The writer also asked permission and assistance from the school principals and school heads to conduct the survey to all teachers in Sagbayan District.

Furthermore, after having sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and District Supervisor, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the respondents. The said research tool's distribution was treated with confidentiality. The respondents were asked to respond honestly all the items on the survey. Out of one hundred seventy-nine (179) questionnaires, only one hundred forty-eight (148) were retrieved. Some of the respondents said that they would not answer the questionnaire since they are already retiring from the service, and others just refused to answer them.

Having the questionnaires retrieved, the writer with the help of his/her statistician tallied and collated the data in tables. The data gathered were subjected to statistical treatment. After having done with the statistical treatment, the analysis and interpretation of data followed.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were used to treat the independent and dependent variables as follows:

In determining the frequency of responses on Age and Gender, Frequency count and simple percentage was used.

In determining the problems met by the teachers in the implementation of modular learning and the observance of the eight roles of teachers, the weighted Mean was used.

In determining the degree of difference between the problems met by the teachers on modular distance learning regarding their profile and the difference on the observance of the eight roles in regard to their profile, the Chi-squared test of independence was used.

In determining the significant correlation between the problems met by the teachers on modular distance learning towards their observance of the eight roles, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was used.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the findings of the study, their analysis and interpretation. It covers the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex distribution and length of service, problems met on modular distance learning, observance of the eight roles of teachers, difference between observance of the eight roles of teachers and problems met on modular distance learning when grouped into profile of the respondents, and the relationship between the problems met by the teachers on modular distance learning and their observance of the eight roles.

Profile of Teachers as to Age, Gender, and Length of Service

As the intervening variables, the age, gender, and length of service profile of the respondents must be taken into consideration to determine their demographic distribution.

Table 1.1 Age

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage
22-27	17	11.49
28-33	36	24.32
34-39	48	32.43
40-45	23	15.54
46-51	6	4.05
52-57	15	10.14
58-63	3	2.03
Total	148	100

Table 1.1 reveals that thirty-six (36) or 24.32% of the respondents were at the age bracket 28-33 years old; forty-eight (48) or 32.43% of the respondents were at the age bracket 34-39. This means that majority of the respondents have an age ranging from 28-39 years old. Furthermore, none were below 22 years old and above 63 years old. According to Petry (2002), the age of young adults are 18-35 years old, middle-aged adults are 36-55 years old and older adults are 56 years old and above. This means that the majority of the respondents of this study belongs to the young and middle-aged adults. This is supported by the study of Francisco (2020) that majority of the teachers are at the age of 31-40 which belongs to the young age and middle-aged adults.

Table 1.2 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	12	8.11
Female	136	91.89
Total	148	100

This table reveals that there are one hundred thirty-six (136) or 91.89% female respondents. This means that majority of the respondents are female. As cited by Bongco and Ancho (2020), 87.54% of the teachers in the Philippines at the primary levels are females based on the World Bank Data as of 2016. This reflects a national trend in the feminization of the teaching profession, especially in the elementary level. The high representation of female teachers may influence the dynamics of classroom management, communication styles, and instructional strategies.

Table 1.3 Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
0-5 years	36	24.32
6-10 years	50	33.78
11 years and above	62	41.89
Total	148	100

This table reveals that there were thirty-six (36) respondents with the length of service of 0-5 years, fifty (50) respondents with the length of service of 6-10 years and sixty-two (62) respondents with the length of service of 11 years and above. This means that majority of the respondents in the belongs to experienced teachers. According to Langguyuan-Kadtong, & Usop, (2013), the mean length of service of the teachers in the Philippines at the time their study was conducted was 11.81 years.

Problems Met on Modular Distance Learning

As the independent variable of this study, problems met by teachers on modular distance learning should be considered to determine if they really influenced the dependent variable. These problems include challenges in module distribution, student engagement, instructional delivery, and feedback mechanisms. Understanding these concerns helps determine whether they hinder teachers from effectively fulfilling their professional responsibilities. Examining the correlation between these problems and the eight roles of teachers is essential to assess the resilience and adaptability of educators during educational disruptions.

Table 2. Problems Met on Modular Distance Learning

PROBLEMS MET BY RESPONDENTS	Mean	SD	Description
1. Teachers received inappropriate approaches and complaints if the students do not understand the modules.	2.70	0.84	Agree
2. Teachers encountered discourteous attitude of the students.	2.73	0.89	Agree
3. Teachers failed to communicate and guide the students easily due to poor access	2.81	0.83	Agree
4. Teachers do not receive the answer sheets on time.	3.08	0.68	Agree
5. Teachers do not appreciate/recognized the effort of students in answering the modules	2.29	0.94	Disagree
6. Teachers are not well-oriented in delivering modules.	2.03	0.92	Disagree
7. Teachers cannot finish printing, sorting, and organizing SLMs for the succeeding weeks	2.08	0.87	Disagree
8. Teachers are facing a dangerous path every day within the modular learning setup.	2.37	0.89	Disagree
9. Teachers had no proper training in the use of technology needed for learning dissemination.	2.29	0.90	Disagree
10. Teachers are not good in using any device for distance learning approach.	2.23	0.89	Disagree
11. Inability of the teachers to cope with the prepared tools for modular distance learning approach	2.28	0.78	Disagree
12. The low access of the teachers in discussing their lessons towards their students due to poor internet connectivity at particular location.	3.14	0.83	Agree
13. Difficulties on the side of the teacher to discuss the lesson if the student is slow learner.	3.26	0.69	Strongly Agree
14. Uneasiness for the teacher to identify students who hardly work for the answers	3.22	0.72	Agree
15. Teachers unable to manage students from time to time.	3.07	0.75	Agree
16. Teachers who are not good in terms of using gadgets, smart phones, etc.	2.53	0.95	Agree
17. Hidden cost/expenses of the teacher towards modules.	2.95	0.80	Agree
18. Problems with the equipment ex. (printing, copies etc.)	3.11	0.79	Agree
19. It would be hard for the teacher to explain thoroughly the modules given without further examples.	3.16	0.75	Agree
20. Teachers have no longer time to re check the content of the module because of the busy loads.	3.14	0.77	Agree
Composite	2.72	0.92	Agree

As shown in table 2, the statements “Difficulties on the side of the teacher to discuss the lesson if the student is slow learner and difficult to identify learners independent work.” got the highest weighted mean of 3.26 ($SD=0.68$) and 3.22 ($SD=0.83$) respectively was described as “agree” for problems towards modular distance learning. These means that teachers’ main problem in the conduct of modular distance learning is how to deal with the slow learners since there is no face-to-face interaction where teachers can further explain the lesson to every learner. The absence of real-time feedback and guided instruction makes it more difficult for struggling students to catch up with the lessons. As a result, teachers experience additional challenges in monitoring learning progress and ensuring that students understand the content of the modules.

Moreover, the statements “Teachers do not receive the answer sheets on time and poor internet connectivity” followed with a weighted mean of 3.08 ($SD=0.69$) and 2.81 ($SD=0.72$) respectively and was described as “agree”. Teachers agreed that they have failed to communicate and guide the students due to poor access in which they have inevitably encountered discourteous attitudes of the learners. Teachers admitted that they received inappropriate approaches and complaints if the learner do not understand the modules which eventually lead to not receiving the answer sheets on time. This situation has caused delays in checking and providing feedback, further affecting the teaching-learning process.

Furthermore, problems met on modular distance learning got a weighted mean of 2.72 ($SD=0.92$) which was described as “agree”. This is in accordance with the study of Alvarez (2021), that the teacher ran into several issues when implementing modular learning and the roles that teachers should play. These include poor communication, student misconduct, insufficient teacher guidance, disrespectful behavior toward teachers, and student complaints about not understanding the modules. Thus, this means that teachers were bothered on how they are going to deal with those problems and how they are going to manage classes during those difficult times.

Observance of the Eight Roles of Teachers

As the dependent variable of this study, the eight roles of teachers should be considered to determine whether this is affected by other variables of this study. These roles—such as facilitator, evaluator, motivator, planner, and manager—are essential in shaping the quality of teaching and student learning outcomes. Evaluating how teachers perform these roles during modular distance learning can provide insight into their adaptability and resilience amid educational disruptions. Understanding the influence of external factors on these roles also helps inform policymaking and capacity-building programs. Moreover, assessing the observance of these roles allows stakeholders to identify areas that may require additional support, training, or intervention to maintain teaching effectiveness during times of crisis.

Table 3. Observance of the Eight Roles of Teachers

	Mean	SD	Description
INFORMATION PROVIDER			
1. Conduit for information-transmitting information to students	4.06	0.72	Much Observed
2. Curator of information filtering and making information available	4.09	0.76	Much Observed
Composite	4.08	0.74	Much Observed
FACILITATOR AND MENTOR			
1. Information coach-guiding students to ask the right question, source information and evaluate information received	3.76	0.85	Much Observed
2. Clarifying learning outcomes	3.82	0.81	Much Observed
3. Identifying appropriate learning opportunities	3.82	0.81	Much Observed
4. Making learning effective and efficient	3.86	0.88	Much Observed
5. Engaging and motivating the students by serving as a mentor	3.87	0.85	Much Observed
Composite	3.83	0.84	Much Observed
ASSESSOR AND DIAGNOSTICIAN			
1. Plan and implement assessments of for your course learners	3.89	0.71	Much Observed
2. Monitor students' performance and progress	3.71	0.76	Much Observed
3. Decide about learners' performance and progress	3.99	0.72	Much Observed
4. Provide feedback to students	3.72	0.77	Much Observed
5. Evaluate and change the assessment where necessary	3.93	0.74	Much Observed
Composite	3.85	0.75	Much Observed
CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTER AND DEVELOPER			
1. Be familiar with the school's approach to assessment	3.99	0.72	Much Observed
2. Be familiar with the school's curriculum	4.09	0.71	Much Observed
3. Plan and implement your own course in line with the school's curriculum	3.80	0.84	Much Observed
4. Evaluate the curriculum and plan for changes	3.84	0.81	Much Observed
Composite	3.93	0.78	Much Observed
ROLE MODEL			
1. Influences students' lifestyle choices	3.71	0.78	Much Observed
2. Influences students' career choices	3.72	0.77	Much Observed
3. Contributes to a learning environment that supports students' learning	3.95	0.69	Much Observed
Composite	3.79	0.75	Much Observed
MANAGER AND LEADER			
1. Engaging with the decision-making process	3.87	0.68	Much Observed
2. Managing elements in the curriculum	3.77	0.73	Much Observed
3. Supporting change and overcoming obstacles	3.82	0.65	Much Observed
Composite	3.82	0.69	Much Observed
SCHOLAR AND RESEARCHER			
1. Identifying what works and what does not work	3.86	0.68	Much Observed
2. Applying evidence to practice	3.86	0.70	Much Observed
3. Research and innovation	3.62	0.76	Much Observed
4. Sharing your experiences with others	3.94	0.73	Much Observed
Composite	3.82	0.73	Much Observed
PROFESSIONAL			
1. Acquisition of necessary competencies and keeping up to date	3.95	0.61	Much Observed
2. Supporting personal well-being	4.02	0.62	Much Observed
3. "Civic" professionalism	4.01	0.62	Much Observed
Composite	4.00	0.62	Much Observed
Overall	4.00	0.62	Much Observed

As shown in table 3, the curator of information got the highest weighted mean of 4.09($SD=0.76$) for the role “information provider”. For the role “facilitator and mentor”, the item “engaging and motivating the students by serving as a mentor” got the highest weighted mean of 3.87 ($SD=0.85$) which is marked as much observed. In the role assessor and diagnostician, the item “deciding about learners’ performance and progress” got the highest weighted mean of 3.99 ($SD=0.72$) which is marked as much observed. For the role curriculum implementer and developer, the item “familiarize with the school’s curriculum” got the highest weighted mean of 4.09 ($SD=0.71$) which was described as much observed. As a role model, the item “contributes to a learning environment that supports students’ learning” got the highest weighted mean of 3.95 ($SD=0.69$) which is described as much observed. Furthermore, as manager and leader, the item “engaging with the decision-making process” got the highest weighted mean of 3.87 ($SD=0.68$) which was described as much observed. Moreover, as a scholar and researcher, the item “sharing experiences with others got the highest weighted mean of 3.94 ($SD=0.73$) which was described as much observed. Lastly, as a professional, the item “supporting personal well-being got the highest weighted mean of 4.02 ($SD=0.62$) which was described as much observed.

Of all the eight roles of teachers, the item “Curator of information filtering and making information available which is under the role information provider” got the highest weighted mean of 4.09 ($SD=0.76$) was described as “much observed”. This means that the most observed role during the conduct of modular distance learning is being an information provider. This is in contrast in the study of Koca et. al (2021) that “information provider and coach” got significantly lower scores compared to the rest of the roles.

Based on the results, the observance of the roles of teachers during the conduct of modular distance learning got a composite of 4.00 ($SD=0.62$) described as “much observed”. This means that majority of the roles are still present even in abnormal situation. According to the study of Saxena (2020), with learning shifting from public space to a more personal area, the role of the educator has also evolved. As teaching and learning become more personalized, teachers come up with innovative teaching methodologies on a case-to-case basis to suit to their learners’ needs.

Difference Between the Observance of the Eight Roles of Teacher, and the Problems Met by Teachers on Modular Distance Learning when grouped into Profile of the Respondents

This table determines if the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex and length of service is statistically related to the eight roles of teachers and the problems met by teachers and on modular distance learning. The statistical treatment used was Chi-square to determine the significance of the difference between the variables.

Table 4.1 The Difference Between the Eight Roles of Teachers When Grouped into their Profile

Profile	χ^2	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	16.28	18	.570	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Gender	1.63	3	.650	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Length of Service	7.76	6	.260	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho

Table 4.1 presents that there is no significant difference between the age and eight roles of teachers, $\chi^2(18, N=148) = 16.28, p=.570$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This indicates that teachers' roles do not differ regardless of age. According to of study of Shah et al. (2018) that age does not apparently affect perceived teaching effectiveness. This means that teachers age effects do not increase even at the middle age and will not affect the roles of teachers.

Table 4.1 also reveals that there is no significant difference between gender and eight roles of teachers, $\chi^2(3, N=148) = 1.63, p=.650$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that roles of teachers do not vary no matter what gender a teacher has. Wood (2012) concluded that there is no significant difference between male and female elementary teachers. It can be concluded that male and female teachers have the same role in the teaching and learning process.

Lastly, the relationship of length of service on the eight roles of teachers is statistically not significant, $\chi^2(6, N=148) = 7.76, p=.260$. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This is in contrast in the study of Melnick et al. (2008) that beginning teachers are more prepared than experienced teachers in using assessment methods. Experienced teachers also feel better prepared to communicate with parents about the child's progress and utilized multiple methods of communication with parents.

Table 4.2 The Difference Between Problems Met by Teachers on Modular Distance Learning Approach When Grouped into their Profile

Profile	χ^2	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	19.89	18	.340	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Sex	5.27	3	.150	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Length of Service	5.56	6	.470	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho

Table 4.2 shows no significant difference age and between problems met on modular distance learning, $\chi^2(18, N=148) = 19.89, p=.340$. This means that the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that no matter what the age of the teachers, their coping abilities to the problems they met in teaching are the same.

This is in contrast in the study of Chaturvedi and Purushothaman (2019) said that teachers aging 40-60 years old can cope better with problems and job stress compared to younger ones.

Table 4.2 also shows no significant difference between gender and problems met on modular distance learning approach, $\chi^2(3, N=148) = 5.27, p = .150$. This means that the null hypothesis is not rejected. Regardless of gender, problems met by the teachers are the same. Kazmi and Chaudhry (2015) found no significant difference between male and female teachers in coping with job strains except female teachers seek more emotional support compared to male teachers. It just means that teachers regardless of sex can cope with the problems related to their teaching job.

Lastly, table 4.2 shows no significant difference between length of service and problems met by teachers, $\chi^2(6, N=148) = 5.56, p = .470$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This is in contrast in the study of Harmsen et al. (2017) that beginning teachers seems to be more vulnerable to the pressures of the profession compared to the experienced teachers. Although, experienced teachers are better than beginning teachers in terms of coping to problems but the length of service of teachers does not define what problems they will meet along the way in the teaching and learning process.

The Relationship of Problems Met on Modular Distance Learning and the Eight Roles of Teachers

This table determines if the independent variable, which is problems met on modular distance learning affects the dependent variable, which is the eight roles of teachers.

Table 5. The Relationship of Problems Met on Modular Distance Learning and the Eight Roles of Teachers

Variables	<i>r</i>	α	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation	Decision
Problems Met on modular Distance Learning and Eight Roles of Teachers	-.02	.05	.810	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho

Table 5 shows the relationship between problems met and eight roles of teachers. As shown in the table, the overall problems met and eight roles of teachers is not statistically significant, $r(146) = -.02, p = .810$. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. According to Barron et al. (2021), the new set up in the education system is helping the teachers by sharing guidelines on how to provide feedback to students, maintain constant communication and report local education departments for keeping the track of learning. Although teachers met different problems along the way during the implementation of

modular distance learning, but as they go through the process, they learned how to adjust their roles depending on the situation.

Findings

The study revealed the following findings:

- 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents:** Most of the respondents were between 34–39 years old. A significant portion, one hundred thirty-six (136) or 91.89%, were female, and sixty-two (62) respondents had more than 11 years of teaching experience. This profile suggests that the study involved experienced and predominantly female educators.
- 2. Problems Encountered in Modular Distance Learning:** Teachers reported several key issues in the implementation of modular distance learning. These included delayed return of answer sheets from students, poor internet connectivity, difficulty in assisting slow learners, and challenges in identifying students' independent work due to the lack of face-to-face interaction.
- 3. Level of Observance of the Eight Roles of Teachers:** Respondents indicated a high level of observance of the eight roles of teachers, with an overall weighted mean of 4.0. The “information provider” role garnered the highest mean rating of 4.09, reflecting the teachers' consistent engagement in delivering knowledge despite modular learning challenges.
- 4. Relationship Between Teachers' Profile and Study Variables:** Statistical analysis revealed no significant difference in the problems encountered and the observance of the eight roles of teachers when grouped according to respondents' age, sex, and length of service. This implies that these demographic variables did not influence the extent of challenges faced or role performance.
- 5. Correlation Between Learning Challenges and Teacher Roles:** The study found no significant relationship between the problems met in modular distance learning and the observance of the eight roles of teachers. This suggests that regardless of the challenges, teachers were able to maintain their professional roles effectively.

Conclusions

Delayed return of answer sheets from students, poor internet connectivity, hard to deal with slow learners, and difficulty on the side of the teachers to identify learners' independent works were the main problems faced by the teachers in the implementation of modular distance learning. The Department of Education may allow limited teacher-learner interaction and allow teachers to create localized learning modules that would fit the needs of the academically challenged learners. This will also help those academically challenged learners get modules that will fit in their level. However, the modules must be

validated, at least by the district quality assurance team, to ensure the correctness of the modules. On the other hand, teachers' roles especially the role model got the lowest scores compared to other roles of teachers. The department of education may conduct training on how to keep teachers' role as role model despite crisis.

Recommendations

Considering the salient findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended by the researchers.

- 1. Empowering Teachers through Module Autonomy:** The Department of Education is encouraged to grant teachers greater autonomy in designing instructional modules, recognizing their direct engagement with learners and contextual understanding of their academic needs. Allowing teachers to customize content ensures that modules are developmentally appropriate and responsive to the needs of academically challenged learners, ultimately improving learning outcomes.
- 2. Adoption of Purok-Based Distribution System:** Schools are advised to implement a localized *purok* system for the efficient distribution and retrieval of learning modules. This community-based strategy can help minimize delays in the return of answer sheets, increase parental involvement, and enhance the logistical flow of modular learning in geographically dispersed areas.
- 3. Strengthening Home Visitation and Intervention Programs:** School administrators are encouraged to institutionalize home visitation and targeted intervention initiatives for learners with late submissions and low performance. These follow-up activities will enable teachers to provide remedial instruction, reinforce lessons, and build stronger partnerships with parents in supporting learners' academic progress.
- 4. Monitoring of Teachers' Role Performance:** The Department of Education should establish a structured mechanism for monitoring the implementation of the eight roles of teachers during modular learning. By evaluating their execution, DepEd can identify gaps, address teacher concerns more effectively, and reinforce their professional growth amid evolving educational demands.
- 5. Capability-Building on Teacher Role Modeling:** DepEd and school administrators may design and conduct focused training programs to strengthen teachers' role modeling, especially in the context of distance learning. Since this role was identified as less visible during modular delivery, professional development initiatives should emphasize values formation, ethical conduct, and inspirational teaching.
- 6. Implementation of Action Plan for Academically Challenged Learners:** Schools are encouraged to adopt a comprehensive action plan that addresses the

specific learning needs of underperforming students. This plan should include differentiated instruction, accessible remediation tools, and collaborative stakeholder engagement to ensure no learner is left behind.

- 7. Expansion of Research to Include Online Learning Modalities:** Future researchers are advised to consider comparative studies that explore both modular and online distance learning. Such research could reveal differences in how teachers fulfill their roles across modalities, providing valuable insights for policy enhancements and training design.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher ensured that all ethical protocols were properly observed. Permission and informed consent were secured from the school administrators, who affixed their signatures to signify their voluntary agreement to participate as respondents. The researcher emphasized adherence to the basic principles of ethical research, such as anonymity, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. All participants were clearly informed of their rights and the objectives of the study, including their right to withdraw from participation at any time. Proper data management and the utmost confidentiality of the gathered information were assured throughout the research process.

To further ensure the integrity of the research, the study underwent an integrity test and citation audit. This process verified that the content of the study was original and free from plagiarism, reinforcing the credibility of the researcher's work.

The respondents of the study were fully informed that participation was purely voluntary. They were given the freedom to withdraw or decline at any point, whether due to health issues, discomfort with the topics discussed, or personal reasons. It was clearly communicated that their decision to participate or not would have no bearing on their previous, current, or future work-related status.

The researcher also clarified that no compensation or payment would be provided for participation. All responses were treated with an adequate level of confidentiality, handled respectfully, and protected with full privacy. The researcher ensured that the participants had a thorough understanding of the Informed Consent Form before proceeding with the study. The entire research process was conducted with transparency, integrity, and strict compliance with the approved research protocol, including the review and clearance issued by the Research Ethics Committee.

THE PROPOSED ACTION PLAN

Creating Localized and Contextualized Learning Modules and Purok System for the Academically Challenged Learners in the Conduct of Modular Distance Learning Approach- An Action Plan

Rationale

Being able to adapt to the changing situations that occur in this everchanging environment is an important capacity for thriving and effective teachers. Teachers were known to be flexible as they can easily adapt to changes brought about by the changing learning modality. Modular distance learning has now become part of our educational system. Though teachers have been informed on Modular distance learning approach through series of webinars and LAC sessions, teachers still encountered different problems especially in catering the slow learners in the implementation of modular distance learning approach. Therefore, the program Creating Localized and Contextualized Learning Modules and Purok System for the Academically Challenged Learners in the Conduct of Modular Distance Learning Approach is necessary. This program aims to create materials that is suited to the level of the academically challenged learners. The abovementioned program will be implemented in the district of Sagbayan and will be given to all public elementary school teachers of the district.

Objectives

This action plan is guided by the following objectives:

1. Create localized and contextualized modules that will fit to the needs of the slow learners during LAC session.
2. Strengthen home visitation approach or the purok system in the implementation of MDL approach.
3. Develop staff capacity to enhance the quality and outcome of students learning during the implementation of MDL approach.

Mechanics of Implementation

With the approval from the examining panel of this proposal, the researcher will provide copies to each of the elementary schools of Sagbayan District.

Apparently, the researcher will explain thoroughly the intent and mechanics of the program at the district administrators meeting by presenting and providing copies of the results of the study. Their feedback and suggestions are highly encouraged to better implement the designed action plan.

Schedule of Implementation

The program implementation depends on the approval and recommendation of the Sagbayan District Administrators. It is better that it will be done and included in the school based in-service training of the teachers.

Monitoring and Evaluation System

The program shall be monitored and evaluated regularly through the teachers' checklist conducted by the school head or school-in-charge in each school to determine the strength and weakness of the implementation and to address the areas for improvement.

Proposed Action Plan for the Crafting of Localized and Contextualized Learning Modules

Objective 1. Create localized and contextualized modules that will fit to the needs of the slow learners during LAC session

Strategies	Actions	Outcomes	Responsible Officials/Persons	Proposed Budget	Timeframe
Create localized and contextualized modules	Conduct LAC sessions on the how to create localized and contextualized modules	Localized and contextualized modules were crafted.	School Administrators and teachers	800.00 (4 reams of bond paper for printing of the localized and contextualized modules)	July 2023
Ensure quality assurance of the teachers-made localized and contextualized modules.	Conduct quality assurance to the localized and contextualized modules made by the teachers	Quality assured learning modules	School Administrators and Quality Assurance Team		July 2023
Make instructional materials based on the localized and contextualized modules	Instructional materials making during	Instructional Materials was created	School Administrators and teachers		August 2023
Promote the value of sharing of expertise and experiences	Provide additional technical support to cover the increasing needs of the teachers and learners	Technical Assistance Form coming from the school administrator and list of shared learning objects	School Administrators and teachers		August 2023-July 2024

Strengthen technological support to teachers as this can help teachers and learners in creating localized modules	Conduct a training on the use of technology in the crafting of localized modules	Teachers were trained in the use of ICT	Teachers and students	Provide funds to support teachers and students' communication	August 2023-July 2024
Objective 2. Intensifying home visitation approach or the purok system in the implementation of MDL approach.					
Provide time for limited face to face interaction between the teacher and the learner to follow-up what is learned from the module	Conduct regular home visitations especially to slow learners to further follow-up their learning outcomes	Learners' attendance sheet and enhanced performance	Teachers and students	Provide funds to support teachers' travel	August 2023-July 2024
Strategize the distribution and retrieval of modules to lessen the delayed return of the answer sheets.	Conduct purok system approach in the distribution and retrieval of modules	Distribution and retrieval checklist	Teachers and students	Provide funds to support teachers' travel	August 2023-July 2024
Objective 3. Enhance the quality and outcome of students learning during the implementation of MDL approach.					
Provide differentiated activities to the variety of learners	Design meaningful and engaging modular activities through enrichment	Differentiated activities base on the needs of the learners	DepEd		August 2023-July 2024
	activities and utilization of DepEd TV episodes to support learning				
Provide support in engaging activities of the learners and be available always in case there are learners' queries and clarifications.	Encourage learners to utilize online platforms and social media to support learning and be connected to their respective teachers so that problems will be addressed directly.	Survey form on the satisfaction of the learners on the use of social media and online platforms	Teachers	1000 monthly load allowance for the teachers and learners	August 2023-July 2024

Budgetary Requirement for the Enhancement of Teachers' Role in the Implementation of MDLA

Item Expenditure	Quantity (e.g. # of bottles/units/packs)	Cost	Amount
A. Dissemination of the results of the study (May 2023)			
Materials/Supplies	4 reams of short bond paper	Php 800.00	Php 800.00
	1 set Epson Ink	Php 1,200.00	Php 1,200.00
B. Monthly budget for home visitation and purok system implementation (August 2023-July 2024)			
Materials/Supplies	Php 2,000.00 budget from each school from school MOOE	Php 252,000.00	Php 252,000.00
	Php 1,000.00 monthly load allowance per school	Php 126,000.00	Php 126,000.00
C. Application and Feedbacking (every month)			
Materials/Supplies	Covered with monthly budget		
D. Monitoring and Evaluation			
Materials/Supplies	Covered with monthly budget		
Total			Php 381,000.00

REFERENCES

- Alvarez, M. (2021). Issues and concerns of teachers in Mindanao State University-Sulu towards modular distance learning approach [Unpublished manuscript].
- Barron, C., Candelaria, A., & Gonzales, R. (2021). Teachers' experiences in modular distance learning: Challenges and adaptations. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(4), 731–746.
- Bongco, T. R. S., & Ancho, I. V. (2020). Exploring the feminization of the teaching profession in the Philippines. *Journal of Research, Policy & Practice of Teachers and Teacher Education (JRPPTTE)*, 10(2), 25–36.
- Chaturvedi, R., & Purushothaman, R. (2019). Coping mechanisms of secondary school teachers in stressful working conditions. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research*, 8(3), 6–10.
- Francisco, M. T. (2020). Teacher profiles and their relation to performance: A regional view. *Philippine Journal of Education and Development*, 9(1), 57–65.
- Guiamalon, M. T., Saripada, R. I., & Tahir, A. M. (2021). Issues and concerns in the implementation of modular learning modality: A case in Mindanao. *Journal of Humanities and Education Development*, 3(3), 143–150.
- Harmsen, R., Helms-Lorenz, M., Maulana, R., & van Veen, K. (2017). The relationship between beginning teachers' stress causes, stress responses, teaching behaviour and attrition.

- Teachers and Teaching, 24(6), 626–643.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2017.1412413>
- Harden, R. M., & Lilley, P. (2018). *The eight roles of the medical teacher: The purpose and function of a teacher in the healthcare professions* (2nd ed.). Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Kazmi, R., & Chaudhry, A. G. (2015). Occupational stress and coping strategies among teachers of special and general education. *Pakistan Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 13(2), 45–49.
- Koca, S., Büyüköztürk, S., & Cikrikci, O. (2021). The eight roles of teachers: A psychometric assessment. *Journal of Educational Research*, 114(1), 45–61.
- Langguyuan-Kadtong, M., & Usop, A. M. (2013). Work performance and job satisfaction of teachers: Basis for policy formulation. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 2(1), 25–35.
- Melnick, S. A., Darling-Hammond, L., & Newton, X. A. (2008). Preparing teachers for assessment: What teacher candidates learn about student assessment in teacher education. *The Teacher Educator*, 43(4), 229–251.
- Petry, N. M. (2002). A comparison of young, middle-aged, and older adult treatment-seeking pathological gamblers. *The Gerontologist*, 42(1), 92–99.
- Saxena, R. (2020). Evolution of the role of educators in distance learning. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 5–23.
- Shah, S. S., Irfan, M., & Fatima, A. (2018). Age and gender as determinants of teaching effectiveness. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(1), 32–39.
- Wood, R. (2012). Gender equality in education: Impact on student performance. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Research*, 3(2), 16–22.